

**Report on the dissemination
workshop with the Joint
Integrative Project ORION
WP4**

Responsible Partner: SVA

Contributing partners: BfR

GENERAL INFORMATION

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	Other recipient(s): JIP and JRP Project Leaders		

REPORT ON THE DISSEMINATION WORKSHOP WITH THE JOINT INTEGRATIVE PROJECT ORION

Objective

The Joint Integrative Project (JIP) ORION started in 2018 and as it will end in June 2021, it is now in the final phase of the project. In order to disseminate the results from the project, on the 5th of October 2020, ORION and OHEJP WP4 arranged a workshop where the project work packages presented their work. The objective was to allow other OHEJP projects to learn more about the tools and solutions developed by ORION.

ORION: One health suRveillance Initiative on harmOnization of data collection and interpretation

The project focuses on the semantic and technical interoperability between the One Health sectors, with specific focus on surveillance information. The project aims at establishing and strengthening inter-institutional collaboration and transdisciplinary knowledge transfer in the area of surveillance data integration and interpretation, along the One Health objective of improving health and well-being. This is achieved through an interdisciplinary collaboration of 13 veterinary and/or public health institutes from 7 European countries. These agencies are committed to adopt best practice One Health Surveillance (OHS) solutions (guidelines, methods, tools and knowledge).

Invitation

The invitation, as follows below, was sent to all Joint Research Project (JRP) and JIP Project Leaders and deputy Project Leaders, as well as to the OHEJP Project Management Team on August 24 2020, with a reminder on September 28.

“Dear all,

We are delighted to invite you to a workshop with the first call Joint Integrative Project ORION. Several of the second call OHEJP projects have expressed interest in the project’s work and now is the time to offer an opportunity to learn more about the many different outputs ORION has developed and will finalize during its final year.

ORION has supported mutual understanding and information exchange among sectors involved in One Health Surveillance (OHS). ORION has developed a number of resources to support cross sectoral collaboration, knowledge exchange, data interoperability and external communication. These resources are documented in the One Health Codex:

<https://oh-surveillance-codex.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

Understanding that these resources may be useful for integrative and research projects especially in the second round of OHEJP projects, we invite all project coordinators to circulate a link to this Codex to their participant, and investigate whether the resources contained in the Codex can be useful for any of their WP. Projects which make use of these tools in their work, are developing related tools, or would even like to build on these tools, are encouraged to attend the workshop.

The workshop will take place on Monday 5 Oct, 1-4.30 pm on the platform Adobe Connect. Please follow this link to participate:

<https://svasweden.adobeconnect.com/ohejp-cogwheel-workshops/>

Agenda

1-3 pm Presentation by ORION

3-3.15 pm Break

3.15-4.30 pm Q&A session

You do not need to register to this workshop. Hope to see many of you there!

Best wishes,
WP4 and ORION”

Participants

The workshop attracted 20 participants from the JRPs/JIPs, besides the 11 participants from ORION and the 6 participants from the OHEJP administration.

ORION participants

Alessandro Foddai -DTU
Birgitte Helweigh -DTU
Estibaliz Lopez de Abechuco Garrido -BfR
Fernanda Dórea -SVA
Johanne Ellis-Iversen -DTU
Jörn Gethmann -FLI
Karin Lagensen -NVI
Matthias Filter -BfR
Nazareno Scaccia -BfR
Thomas Selhorst -BfR
Taran Skjerdal -NVI

OHEJP administration

Karin Artursson -OHEJP WP4, SVA
Manuela Canica - OHEJP WP4, INSA
Marie Nyvist -OHEJP WP4, SVA
Jade Passey -OHEJP CommsTeam, UoS
Elaine Campling -OHEJP CommsTeam, UoS
Ludovico Sepe -OHEJP WP5, BfR

JRP/JIP participants

Ana de la Torre
Aura Andreasen
Beatrice Boniotti
Brian Lassen
Carljin Bogaardt
Channie Kahl Petersen
Dariusz Wasyl
Diana Connor
Adriano Di Pasquale
Esther Sundermann
Jens Kirk
Laurent Guillier
Mike Brouwer
Nao Takeuchi-Storm

Pieter-Jan Ceysens
Pikka Jokelainen
Robert Opitz
Tania Rosado
Vera Manageiro
Wim van der Poel

The workshop

The first part of the workshop was recorded and the recording can be found [here](#). The Power Point presentation can be found [here](#).

1. Introduction to ORION, the surveillance pathway and barriers to OH implementation in Europe, the creation of the OH dimensions in the OHS Codex - a resource to share e.g. technical solutions, tools, guidance, experiences (Matthias Filter, ORION Project Leader)

The OHS Codex is a framework that helps to establish and strengthen inter-institutional collaboration and transdisciplinary knowledge transfer in the area of surveillance data integration and interpretation, along the One Health (OH) objective of improving health and well-being. It can be accessed [here](#).

2. Collaboration principle introduction (Johanne Ellis-Iversen and Estibaliz Lopez de Abechuco Garrido)

- Inspiration catalogue - "[Inspiration and Ideas: One Health Integration in Surveillance](#)" (00:19:00 in the recording)
- [The OHEJP Glossary](#) - an extensive list of OHS related terms and definitions. Link to an introduction to the tool and additional services connected to it can be found [here](#) (00:29:45 in the recording)

3. Knowledge principle introduction (Thomas Selhorst, Jörn Gethmann and Karin Lagesen)

- [Knowledge base epi](#) -an inventory of existing surveillance systems, a database that provides an overview of the common statistical methods used for surveillance data within the EU and a literature database gathering reports, scientific literature, and web resources (00:43:30 in the recording)
- Knowledge base NGS -[One Health Sequencing for Surveillance Handbook](#): a web-based resource containing best practice advice and hands on experience for how to set up and use sequencing for surveillance in a OH-supporting manner (00:58:18 in the recording).

4. Data principle (Fernanda Dórea, 1:06:20 in the recording)

- [Health Surveillance Ontology](#) -creating the ability to attach context to data (1:12:36 in the recording)
- Tools to annotate data and metadata to achieve FAIRness. A tool for semantic annotation of data in Excel, and subsequent export of the data in Resource Description Framework (RDF) format. Codes for developers, as well as a guide to install the plug-in for users are available at <https://github.com/RealEstateCore/ExcelRDF>

5. Dissemination principle (Matthias Filter, Estibaliz Lopez de Abechuco Garrido and Johanne Ellis-Iversen, 1:20:20 in the recording)

- [One Health Consensus Report Annotation Checklist](#) (OH-CRAC) -provides a proposal on how to structure metadata in order to help harmonizing surveillance metadata (1:25:15 in the recording)
- National OHS report template -to support One Health reporting, examples or templates to report different types of hazards with a OH focus are being developed (1:33:45 in the recording)

6. OH pilots and wrap up (Fernanda Dórea, 1:39:38 in the recording)

- National pilots in Belgium, Denmark, Germany, Netherlands, Norway, Sweden and the United Kingdom to implement the tools in practice

Break

7. Questions and answers session

Conclusion

The dissemination of the outcomes from the JIPs is of vital importance in order to reach impact within the relevant OH sectors. This workshop was one mean to allow the OHEJP consortium to learn more about the tools developed by ORION. The concept worked well and will, in all probability, be repeated for other JIPs as well in the future.